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Glossary, abbreviations and acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
CR	Crossroad
WOPA	Working Paper
TILLs	Technology Innovation Law Labs
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
SSSA	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
CNR	National Research Council of Italy
UL	University of Luxembourg
UT3	Université Toulouse III – Paul Sabatier
JU	Jagiellonian University
ESR	Early Stage Researcher
IT	Information Technology
IP	Intellectual Property
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
Q	Question
A	Answer
PNG	Portable Network Graphics (image format)
PDF	Portable Document Format
ID	Identifier
SOTA	State of the Art
ChatGPT	Chat Generative Pre-trained Transformer (AI language model)
Zenodo	Open-access repository for research data and publications

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the work carried out for the development of four boardgames based on the four Crossroads of the LeADS project: (1) Privacy and Intellectual Property; (2) Trust in Data Processing and Algorithm Design; (3) Data Ownership; (4) Empowering Individuals. The boardgames translate the knowledge that has been generated throughout the Crossroads' collaborative work, the Working Papers (WOPAs), the secondment periods and the Technology Innovation Law Lab, into practical tools that spark discussions and enable dissemination and engagement with the wider public. For each boardgame, the methodology for their development is described and the corresponding kits of materials for playing them are provided.

1 Introduction

One of the key goals of the LeADS project is transferring the interdisciplinary and intersectoral knowledge that has been generated during (a) the secondment periods carried out at the partners' institutions, (b) the individual and collaborative work carried out within the four Crossroads (CRs) and the Working Papers (WOPAs) about key issues that are currently at the forefront of discussion in the international law and technology community and (c) the Technology Innovation Law Lab (TILLs), into practical tools that go beyond traditional academic knowledge production. This is why the Crossroads' discussion games have been developed with the double aim of (i) enabling the transfer of scientific knowledge through the application of the soft and hard skills that have been acquired and of (ii) raising general awareness by inviting the wider public to participate in current discussions on key controversial issues at the intersection of law and technology that also have societal implications.

This deliverable reports the methodology for developing four discussion games (i.e., the LeADS-Crossroads Board Games) on the topics explored and debated within the four Crossroads (published in D3.1 and D5.1) and the WOPAs (published in D5.2), namely: (1) Privacy and Intellectual Property; (2) Trust in Data Processing and Algorithm Design; (3) Data Ownership; (4) Empowering Individuals.. In the Annexes, it also displays the materials that are necessary to play the games (i.e., the kits to print the games). By making the games available online and by organizing events to engage the wider public, the impact of the knowledge generated within the project will also be strengthened. The plan foresees two opportunities for disseminating the games. The project members have organized a public playtest session at one of the partners' institutions (i.e., the VUB) in January 2024. The second event will be organized in the second part of the year 2024, for example during the Researchers' Nights. Such occasions will also be valuable to test the games with members of the intended audience and gather useful feedback to enhance the game mechanics in the future.

Designing a game requires a thorough and careful definition of the structure, objectives and elements that can bring the intended players to reach such objectives. This process is iterative since the first hypotheses that are formed need to be tested in practice; and many of them will be discarded as the game design evolves. The games presented in these pages make use of various game mechanics that determine the interactions between players and the game: for instance, they use points to strengthen people's motivation to play and challenges that provide rewards when players successfully complete tasks. The discussion games presented in these pages are a typology of serious games, i.e., games that combine an educational goal with a recreational element. In order to identify the main principles of serious game design, the University of Luxembourg organized a dedicated seminar where Prof. Rod McCall (Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology) presented the differences between serious games and other kinds of games, the main objectives of serious games (i.e., motivational, knowledge acquisition, training and awareness raising), as well as the main mechanics related to rules, players, time, etc. Prof. McCall also provided some indication on how to create and design a serious game and answered the ESRs questions about their own game concepts.

The report is structured as follows: each main section describes the methodological process of developing each LeADS-Crossroad Board Game. The corresponding material (i.e., the board, cards, instructions for playing, instructions for printing, etc.) is shown in the Appendixes.

2 Crossroad 1's boardgame: "Know-IT-all!"

Authors:

CR Leaders: Arianna Rossi (SSSA), Giovanni Comandé (SSSA), Salvatore Rinzivillo (CNR)

ESRs Team: Tommaso Crepax (SSSA), Qifan Yang (SSSA), Mitisha Gaur (SSSA), Onntje Hinrichs (VUB)

2.1 Methodology for the development of the game

The Discussion Board Game is one of the horizontal training tools in the LeADS project. Its objective is to focus on controversial issues that have been developed throughout the research and writing process of the different iterations of the crossroads (D3.2 Introductory Crossroad Report, D5.1 Secondment Crossroad Report) and the Working Papers (D5.2) and to translate some of these results into content that raises awareness and educates the general public about crucial issues in the data economy. The board game therefore constitutes a knowledge transfer from academic research that has been conducted within Crossroad 1 (CR1) towards content that can be understood by the general public. CR1 designed the discussion board game '**Know-IT-all**', a **trivia-board game targeting Information Technologies ('IT')** which engages the players through questions about six (6) primary verticals signified through different colours on the game board, namely- (i) Data as Commodity (Blue) (ii) Privacy (Pink) (iii) Curiosity (Yellow) (iv) IP (Purple) (v) AI (Green) (vi) Big Tech = (Orange). The premise of the game is rooted in the player correctly answering the questions posed to them in each category in order to progress through the game board and collect points. The game culminates based on speed, where the player who answers the most number of questions across categories at the fastest pace wins (See Annex I: Instructions of the game). The game intends to raise awareness and enhance the knowledge of its players as well as spectators by engaging them in discussions pertaining to the questions posed under each category of trivia. Know-IT-all is strongly inspired by the principles of the Socratic method which encourages learning through the asking and answering of questions.

2.1.1 Objectives and Requirements

The members of CR1 developed their board game in an iterative manner over a period of eight weeks, starting in October 2023. After each meeting, individual tasks were assigned to ESRs that had to be completed prior to the following meeting. During the first meeting, the deadlines of the deliverable were highlighted which provided the general time-frame for the development process. During a first brainstorming, each group member presented experiences and prior knowledge of discussion games. From this exchange resulted a first set of game elements and considerations that were regarded as crucial to consider during the development process such as:

- *The target audience*, as this would influence both game mechanics, game design and content. CR1 agreed that target audience are 'laypersons', i.e. people who are neither experts in law nor computer science.
- *General game design*, CR1 agreed that a complex game design easily creates frustration and that the game should therefore be easily accessible to everyone. The group thus decided to keep game mechanics as simple and accessible as possible and to focus on the content of the game instead (see further below).
- *Work plan*, the possibility to delegate tasks and equally distribute the work was considered an important feature in the development of the board game, as well as the possibility to start working simultaneously without "bottlenecks" effects.
- *Modularity*, to help compartmentalize tasks and generate artifacts that could easily be used, reused, and shared (even for different board games from other Crossroads).

After the first meeting, the idea emerged to create a CR1 version of the popular board game [“Trivial Pursuit”](#), where players must collect knowledge tokens by correctly answering questions in different categories. A Trivia-Type game in the likes of Trivial Pursuit was considered to be a valuable option for a number of reasons:

- Scalability: the possibility to add any quantity of questions/answers, including questions based on research from other Crossroads in the LeADS project.
- *Modularity*: the possibility to increment, change, reformulate any of the questions, add expansion packs on the basis of latest findings, or with content related to the LeADS Working Papers, but also to collaborate with other labs/universities/partners/secondment beneficiaries to create personalised packs.
- Tailoring: the possibility to adapt the game to the target audience that plays it (with regard to game difficulty, see below for further details)

2.1.2 Topics and Questions

The first step in the development required to distil six broad categories from the crossroad work. Each ESR proposed categories that he/she thought would reflect major tensions in CR1 and which, at the same time, could be exploited for the purposes of our board game. The propositions were subsequently discussed and narrowed down to the following: (i) Data as Commodity, (ii) Privacy, (iv) IP, (v) AI, and (vi) Big Tech. A sixth category, i.e., (iii) Curiosity, was added to enhance the fun and engaging elements of the game.

The second step consisted in developing questions for each category. The topics for the questions were inspired by, for instance, individual and collective research conducted within Crossroad 1 or by scanning popular Websites such as wired.com, arstechnica.com or techcrunch.com. Most of the development process was devoted to this step since it required the ESRs to constantly review and adapt the question catalogue to ensure that the game remained accessible and engaging for the general public by, for example:

- Avoiding legal concepts or abbreviations in the questions
- Making questions more relatable/engaging (using concrete examples (Facebook does xxx) instead of abstract formulations (Company Y does xxx))
- Reformulating questions and simplifying the language used to make questions understandable by non-experts
- Asking: how do we transform academic questions into interesting/relatable questions for the general public that spark curiosity about the data economy? (for example, by transforming the abstract topic of ‘data ownership’ into a concrete question of ‘what can you do with an e-book which you bought online’)

ESRs reviewed each other’s question to constantly improve and refine this crucial aspect of the game. By the end of this process, ~250 Questions were developed roughly distributed across the six categories. The questions were collected in tabular form (Excel file) and shared among the developers. Each question was assigned a unique ID. Each row of the table therefore contained the unique ID, the TOPIC (and the colour assigned), the first version of the QUESTION, its REFORMULATED version, the answer OPTIONS, the AUTHOR, the REVIEWER, the DIFFICULTY level, and eventually a COMMENTS cell to ask questions or clarifications to the Author. Once the question had been reformulated in an adequate way, the reviewer would green light the REVIEW cell. The last cell in each row was for the classification in questions wither for Experts or for Non-Experts. Such differentiation sought to ensure it would be possible to include difficult questions for players that have domain expertise (e.g., PhD students) at will and therefore adapt the question list to their needs.

These questions were classified as follows:

- As expert / non-expert questions: non-expert questions were defined as such if they agreed with the following statement: a non-expert would be interested in knowing the answer to this question.

- Assigned to a difficulty-level from 1(easy) to 3(difficult). Difficulty 1: Question and answer are or should be known to the public; Difficulty 2: Either Q or A could be known by the public (also in relation to the easiness of excluding obvious wrong options); Difficulty 3: Both Q&A are typically unknown to the public.

The cards were then created with the use of Canva software.¹ After the creation of an initial simple design for a template card showing the ID, the Topic (with the assigned colour), the difficulty level, the Question, the Options and the Answer, thanks to the “bulk create” option, it was possible to automatize the creation of all the cards in sets of Topic. After manual editing and formatting, the cards were saved both in PNG and PDF format to ease the printing process.

2.1.3 Testing

The deliverable constitutes a first version (the core) of the game. The ESRs discussed how the game can be easily amended by, for instance, adding further categories’ (as mentioned, the ‘expansions packs’) to the game or by adding more game elements such as ‘jokers’ (e. g. a 50/50 joker that reveals two answers which are wrong; a ‘ask ChatGPT card’ etc.). Whereas the game design and most importantly its questions have already been beta-tested within a small circle of ESRs, it will be played and further refined (by, for instance, reformulating, deleting, or adding new questions) during the upcoming LeADS meeting that is planned to take place in January 2024 in Brussels. The ESRs are considering transforming the development process and the developed game into a scientific publication.

2.2 Open Science and Open Access

To foster open science, the ESRs decided that the list of questions will be published in an open-source repository in Zenodo and made available to the public for reuse and modification (open access).

2.3 Intellectual Property

Finally, the group discussed IP-related aspects of the game since they used a popular game as inspiration. In order to prevent any infringements of IP rights:

- the group designed their own layout of the board game as well as the cards
- consulted with IP experts from LeADS beneficiary SSSA to ensure that the developed game constituted their own creation and did not copy any creative elements from the original work

2.4 Materials

All the material composing the full board game kit are publicly available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number [10.5281/zenodo.17241880](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17241880).²

Annex I contains:

- Game instructions
- Game board
- An example of Game cards

¹ <https://www.canva.com/>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17241880>

3 Crossroad 2's boardgame: "Jury Trials (Green v Blue)"

Authors:

CR Leaders: Claudia Negri Ribalta (UL), Gabriele Lenzini (UL)

ESRs Team: Xengie Doan (UL), Soumia Zohra el Mestari (UL), Robert Lee Poe (SSSA), Louis Sahi (UT3)

This game is a role-playing game designed for people with a background in law and data privacy. The context of the game is around defending a company's public image against attackers who try to destroy its reputation in a specific scenario case. Participants are divided into two teams: the blue team attacks the strategies of the company trying to harm its public image whereas the green team tries to defend the image of the company and its measures. The solutions and arguments of both teams will be accessed by the jury members who will determine the winners based on how well they defended or attacked the company.

3.1 Methodology for game development

Here we describe how the game was developed, and the goals in mind for the educational aspects. The overall goal and development for this game followed several steps. The primary goal was to incorporate elements of the state-of-the-art (SOTA) and address the challenges related to trust and transparency in data processing and AI, as outlined in the CR2's topic. One key aspect of discussion was the broad scope of domains that these challenges span in CR2 and the complex nature of the concept of "trust." CR2 developed two types of games, a narrative progression game and a role-playing game. Then, members voted on which game to continue working on and the role-playing game won.

3.1.1 Game Dynamics

To facilitate the overall goal with these discussions, the game was designed to have teams and prompts that would spark meaningful conversations. Groups could be of any size, with 5 as the minimum. Additionally, to make the game more enjoyable and engaging, a sense of rivalry was introduced between the two teams. A jury was also included to help decide the winners, as determining which team is "better" is subjective and requires discussion. While the number of players can be flexible, the target audience for this game is university students, specifically those pursuing or having completed a bachelor's degree or higher with interests or expertise in law and/or data privacy. This demographic is generally more familiar with academic concepts and can engage in more advanced discussions.

From an educational perspective, the game provides a platform for participants to delve into various topics such as privacy, fairness, communication, and the complex social context of how they are evaluated by people. There will be informational sheets so people may learn something new. It fosters critical thinking and encourages the use of persuasive public speaking skills. Team collaboration is a crucial aspect of the game, as players must work together within their teams to strategize and respond to the challenges presented. This promotes teamwork and enhances problem-solving skills.

The game's scenario mirrors real-life challenges, making it a valuable educational tool for understanding the societal impacts of technology. It is designed to be both engaging and thought-provoking, catering to players interested in privacy, technology, ethics, and corporate governance.

3.1.2 Testing

Although the first prototype of the game is ready, this section describes the plans for testing and improvement. The game was tested once and was played with 6 participants, two of which did not help develop the game much and offered a new perspective. Feedback included that the concept is quite fun and interesting. However, the requirements were too broad and needed some in depth background to create a strategy for. Also, Defenders (Green) and Attackers (Blue) and Jury could change members after a round and more information was needed to guide players on the objective of each turn.

As such, it was decided to make more specific prompts in the requirements card and give background information in an Information Table. This adds an educational element and can help direct the players, so they are not so lost. However, due to time constraints we have edited 12 cards and will work on more for the final submission. Moreover, the rules were changed to add more fun elements, like letting people change teams after one round concludes, while some confusing rules were clarified. Future work includes updating more card prompts and their related information, in addition to making any edits based on upcoming reviews.

3.2 Materials

All the material composing the full board game kit are publicly available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number [10.5281/zenodo.17242424](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17242424).³

Annex II contains:

- Instructions for printing it out
- Aim of the game
- What's Included?
- How to play
- Scenarios
- Scenario's Definitions
- Information Table (refer to your requirements card)
- Cards

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17242424>.

4 Crossroad 3's boardgame: "SynergyLegal: Legal and Technical Challenges around Data Rights"

Authors:

CR Leaders: Imge Ozcan (VUB), Paul De Hert (VUB), Ali Kandi (UT3)

ESRs Team: Cristian Lepore (UT3), Barbara da Rosa Lazarotto (VUB), Aizhana Abdrassulova (JU)

This card challenge game is crafted for individuals with laypeople's knowledge in the realm of internet-related matters. Each card unveils a thought-provoking challenge rooted in everyday occurrences. Armed with skill cards that furnish essential information, participants must develop a solution to the challenges before them. As the game unfolds, participants strategically wield their skill cards, utilizing the wealth of knowledge at their disposal to formulate solutions. The ensuing interactions foster engaging discussions, transforming the game into a forum for intellectual exploration.

4.1 Methodology

4.1.1 Teamwork

The ESRs gathered in an online meeting and decided on the game premise and objective. They aimed to design a game which raises awareness about harmful data regimes and encourages the players to think and learn about how to manage their data. They presented a preliminary version to the CR Leaders. The CR Leaders provided detailed feedback and suggestions, asking the ESRs to simplify the game, keeping in mind that the target audience is the general public. The CR Leaders also pointed out to some inconsistencies and lack of clarity regarding the game mechanics, elements and set of rules. This feedback helped the ESRs to make better design decisions. They presented another version which was ready for playtesting. We tested the game in our CR group which enabled us to further refine the game. This internal playtesting session was especially useful to reconsider the fun element in the game, strategies, and performance expectation from the players. We carried out the collaborative work through emailing, shared docs, to-do lists and online meetings.

4.1.2 Conceptualizing and designing the game

The Missions (challenges) to be tackled in the game are created around the broad topic of Crossroad 3: Data Ownership. Therefore, the ESRs' research was instrumental in conceptualizing and designing the game.

Besides functioning as a drill and warmup to reflect on harmful data regimes and learn about privacy, security and data protection, the game is structured to also encourage the players to make connections among the familiar and the unfamiliar and put forth a convincing argument. This design decision relies on elements such as two-tier scoring system (see the Game Instructions), Skill cards and basing the accomplishment partly on the discussion skills of the players. We got inspired by classroom discussion strategies such as affinity mapping and contextual conversations while designing the game.

Apart from two sets of cards, the game components also include a playful board which functions to add motivational drives to the game as well as further challenges towards the end. There's a coloured box for each round to be played and some boxes offer the possibility of earning double points, skipping the mission which results in loss of points and towards the end, the challenge of less time to solve the Mission is introduced as players will have gained practice by then. Despite two decks of cards were sufficient for the game premise, we decided to add a board to strengthen the fun element in the game without compromising on coherence and maintaining the cohesion between game elements.

4.1.3 Future work for testing and improvement

So far, we have had the opportunity to test the game in our Crossroad group (with the participation of 3 ESRs and 2 CR Leaders). The LeADS project will hold a playtesting session in Brussels in mid-January 2024, where we will have the opportunity to test our game with external participants. We are curious to test the game with people who have no training or background on privacy and data protection. This playtesting session will enable us to find out if our game is easy to learn and understand and if it is engaging and fun to play. We will ask the players to give us feedback by filling in a brief survey. We aim to improve the game based upon the feedback received during this upcoming playtesting session.

4.2 Materials

Annex III contains:

- Game instructions
- Game board
- Cards
- Score
- Correct answers sheet
- Printing instructions

All the material composing the full board game kit are available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number [10.5281/zenodo.17243159](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17243159).⁴

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17243159>

5 Crossroad 4's boardgame: "Privacylandia"

Authors:

CR Leaders: Elwira Macierzynska-Franaszczyk (JU), Emmanuil Alexakis (UPRC)

ESRs Team: Armend Duzha (UPRC), Maciej Zuziak (CNR), Fatma Sumeysra Dogan (JU), Christos Magkos (UPRC)

This is a role-based game where different players (up to six) take the role of the inhabitants of a fictional town. Each player needs to collaborate with at least another player and uses her/his knowledge in legal and technological domains to solve challenges which an individual being data subject may face in real life. The solutions to the different challenges are presented to the community (composed by the other players) who will assess them and decide on the bonus and/or penalty to be assigned.

5.1 Methodology

5.1.1 Background

The game was inspired by well-known board games (i.e. Monopoly, Snakes and Ladders, etc.) in order to facilitate onboarding the participants and making it more appealing for them. However, the design of the board and the rules have been designed from scratch 1) to further differentiate our game from the class of said games, and 2) to make it relevant to the goals and activities of the Crossroad #4 "Empowering Individuals". Thus, we followed an iterative co-creation process, with different feedback loops and further updates on a weekly basis, under the supervision of the Crossroad leaders (one from legal and one from technical background). Upon discussing central themes regarding data protection, cybersecurity and ethics in the setting of data processing and management questions were generated by the ESRs and then fitted into daily scenarios individuals could encounter.

5.1.2 Game dynamics

More information can be found in Appendix IV. However, we would like to emphasise that we designed the game having in mind the active participation and engagement of different players that bring together different experiences and skills from legal and technical fields. To add more elements of "gamification" we have introduced bonus and penalty cards to foster the dialogue for identifying the best solution to the challenges presented on the board and incentivize performance and discussion among players. Also, all the location fields have been selected in order to enrich the "story": each of them will include a brief text describing real-world data processing scenarios. The scenarios were designed to enable critical thinking and a general grasp of ethical and legal principles surrounding data and analytics enabling everyone to participate on an equal footing.

5.1.3 Number of players

A total of 6 players divided into teams of minimum 2 members. Hence, there can be 2 teams of 3 members or 3 teams of 2 members. Some guidelines on team building requirements will be detailed in the game instructions.

5.1.4 A discussion game

We believe it is a discussion game because it includes different activities (e.g. the challenges) that require the collaboration and feedback of different players, meant to foster fruitful debate and creative solutions to real life scenarios. The solutions are first discussed within the team and then presented to the other players (the "community"), who will have to evaluate the solution; in case one or more participants from the community is not satisfied with the outcome presented, he/she will have to justify why they don't agree and possibly suggest / recommend some elements that should have been included / taken into account. The community decides the bonus or penalty to be assigned for each specific case. The player will then extract randomly from the card deck (one for the bonuses and one for penalties, respectively). Not engaging players, regardless of the team they are involved with, will be penalised by the community and this

might also affect the other members of the same team. The team members of the non-engaging player cannot veto the penalty.

5.1.5 Topics

The topics are directly or indirectly related to the CR4 topics as well as individual ESR research. In addition, we prepared the questions by taking into account the implications of current debates in data protection law on individuals' lives as well as common data protection related caveats that may occur in daily life.

5.1.6 Testing

Small simulations have been made in order to check whether the proposed time (1 hour) was enough to allow each player to get the chance to play at least one round (e.g. meaning they have the chance to launch the dice and move in the board) - Thus, having the chance to directly contribute positively or negatively to the team's progress in the game.

We plan to have a full test before the January event in Brussels in order to make the final adjustments.

5.2 Materials

Annex IV contains:

- Board
- Instructions
- Cards
- Challenges
- Bonus
- Penalty
- Personas
- Challenges

All the material composing the full board game kit are available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number: [10.5281/zenodo.17250821](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17250821).⁵

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17250821>

6 Conclusions

The serious games that have been developed within each Crossroad vary greatly in terms of the game mechanics that are involved, thereby revealing the creative efforts that were dedicated to the design of these artefacts. This task has given the ESRs the opportunity to transform the theoretical and practical knowledge, as well as the hard and the soft skills that they have acquired over the years into tangible artefacts that are meant to be used, and enjoyed, by the wider public. Creating serious games on the controversial topics of the Crossroads has proven a highly challenging task, as one needs to find the right balance between educational elements and engaging elements on complex matters. On the one hand, the games have the goal of enhancing knowledge and skills of players; on the other hand, they need to do so with innovative ways that make use of entertaining elements that raise the players' motivation to keep playing and reaching the end of the game. The planned opportunities to present and test the games with the wider public will provide relevant indication on whether that delicate balance has been achieved.

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex I: Crossroad 1's game

7.1.1 Game instructions

Legality Attentive
Data Scientists

Know-IT-all

Funded by
the European Union

EQUIPMENT

1 playing board, 1 dice, 1 card holder, 6 track pawns, 6 scoring tokens, 240 Question-and-Answer cards

THE SETUP

1. Unfold the playing board and place it in the center of the playing area.
2. Each player selects a token and places it on the starting space.
3. Separate the question cards into six categories. Shuffle each pile of question cards and place them face-down.

GAMEPLAY

- ☆ The player with the first turn rolls the die and moves the pawn the indicated number of spaces in any direction on the board.
- ☆ When a player lands on a colored space, an opponent picks up the corresponding category card and asks the question from that category.
- ☆ If the player answers the question correctly, move the track pawn and keep rolling; if the answer is incorrect, the turn passes to the next player.
- ☆ The first player or team to collect all six category wedges and reach the center of the board by exact count wins the game.

Team Discussion Mode: Play team vs.team! 2 or more people per team have 30 seconds to discuss each question. When ready, the representative of the team gives the answer.

OBJECTIVE

Serious Pursuit is designed to spread awareness and deepen understanding about crucial topics related to **Privacy Protection, Regulation of Big Tech, Data as A Commodity, Curiosity, Artificial Intelligence, and Intellectual Property.**

Players will engage in a fun and educational trivia game to challenge their knowledge and ...add some more!

QUESTION CATEGORIES	
BLUE	Data as a Commodity
PINK	Privacy
YELLOW	Curiosity
PURPLE	Intellectual Property
GREEN	Artificial Intelligence
ORANGE	Big Tech

4. Place all of the wedges in a pile by the playing board.
5. Each player or team rolls the die, and the player with the highest roll goes first.

OUR TEAM

The game was designed and organised by members of the Crossroad 1 Team from the LeADS project.

This game is developed for non-commercial, research-based purpose and is based on the game Trivial Pursuit®. The layout of the game board, playing instructions, and other design elements featured as a part of the game are protected under copyright law and are owned by Horn Abbott Ltd. The registered trademarks namely, Trivial Pursuit®, the distinctive design of the gameboard and game cards, Horn Abbot®, and related intellectual property rights are owned by Hasbro, Inc.

7.1.2 Game board

Know-IT-All!

The Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Innovative Training Networks. Grant Agreement ID: 956562

7.1.3 Game cards

Sample Cards from each category of the game:

AI1 Artificial Intelligence 2 N

What makes virtual assistants like Amazon's Alexa, Apple's Siri, and Google Assistant smart? What's the main technology that helps them understand and respond to your commands?

- a) Quantum computing
- b) Augmented reality
- c) Machine learning
- d) Blockchain

Correct answer:

c) Machine learning

BT1 Big Tech 2 E

There's a rule in the European Union about companies behaving fairly. It's in Article 102 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). What does this rule say? What's not allowed when a company is really powerful in the EU?

- a) Small and Medium enterprises cannot create cartels with other SMEs.
- b) Dominant companies cannot engage in environmentally friendly practices.
- c) Large companies in a market cannot engage in practices harming competition and consumers.
- d) State-funded companies cannot participate in private markets.

Correct answer:

c) Large companies in a market from engaging in practices harming competition and consumers.

CU1 Curiosity 1 N

Digital surveillance means using technology to monitor, track, and collect information electronically for surveillance. What could happen to privacy and freedom if a lot of digital surveillance is happening everywhere?

- a) Better protection for personal rights.
- b) Privacy stays pretty much the same.
- c) More chances for misuse and privacy problems.
- d) Less need for keeping information super secure with encryption technology.

Correct answer:

c) More chances for misuse and privacy problems.

DC1 Data as Commodity 2 N

User data, encompassing personal information and behavioral patterns, has become a valuable asset for digital platforms. Concerning the use of user data for commercial purposes by digital platforms, what is the regulation approach of the Digital Markets Act (DMA)?

- a) It encourages unrestricted use of user data
- b) It prohibits all commercial use of user data
- c) It regulates and restricts the commercial use of user data
- d) It mandates that platforms share user data with governments

Correct answer:

c) It regulates and restricts the commercial use of user data.

IP1 Intellectual Property 2 N

In 2014, Facebook bought a super popular messaging app for a whopping \$19 billion. What's the name of that messaging app?

- a) WhatsApp
- b) Snapchat
- c) Instagram
- d) Twitter

Correct Answer:

a) WhatsApp.

PR1 Privacy 1 N

When you want to log into your account, sometimes you need both your password and an extra code sent to your phone. This is called two-factor authentication. What is it?

- a) A type of privacy app
- b) A method to secure your online accounts by requiring two different forms of identification
- c) A popular online video streaming service
- d) A social networking site

Correct Answer:

b) A method to secure your online accounts by requiring two different forms of identification.

The full stack of cards is available at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17241880>

7.2 Annex II: Crossroad 2's game

7.2.1 Instructions for printing it out

Please use A4 sized paper to print out cards. Print more than one copy as needed, e.g., if there are more than 6 player cards.

7.2.2 Aim of the game

This game is a role-playing game designed for people with a background or interest in law and data privacy. The context of the game is around defending a company's public image against attackers who try to destroy its reputation in a specific scenario case present. Participants are divided into two teams: the blue team attacks the strategies of the company trying to harm its public image whereas the green team tries to defend the image of the company and its measures. The solutions and arguments of both teams will be accessed by the jury members who will determine the winners based on how well they defended or attacked the company. This is set in a universe where companies must defend against attackers who try to destroy their reputation in an eternal struggle between Green and Blue to defend their strategies and their trustworthiness and transparency. The goal is to learn about data privacy and legal issues from the requirements prompts and information sheet, and then to discuss the complexity surrounding how they affect trust and transparency. For example, one team may have a solid more technical strategy, but the other team is more persuasive about the effects to data subjects and the Jury can award the point to either team, as long as they explain the reasoning (e.g, Jury A is impressed by the technical strategy, while Jury B is concerned for data subjects and is persuaded more). As the Jury may be quite subjective, players have the chance to switch roles after one round and understand different perspectives. There are various opportunities to change teams and multiple win conditions based on how much time is allotted and how many points are needed.

Duration:

30min or more

Player Characters:

- Jury Member (judges the teams)
- Green team (Players for the company aka "defenders")
- Blue team (Players against the company aka "attackers")

7.2.3 What's Included?

Game elements and descriptions:

- Definition of scenarios
 - Defines terms of the scenario
- Requirement Information table
 - Gives background information about the requirements
- Jury vs Player cards
 - These determine if someone is playing as a jury member or a player. Jury members judge the strategies from the Green and Blue team and determine a winner per round.
- Green vs Blue team cards
 - Of the players, these determine who is on the Green team (developing a strategy to achieve the requirement card prompt) and Blue team (breaking down the strategy from the green team)
- Scenario cards

- These describe the company and issues they are facing. The teams must tailor their responses to the prompts, such as the types of challenges they are facing and should be addressed.
- Requirement cards
 - These cards cover different goals that the team’s strategy should try to achieve.
- Instruction cards
 - These give general instructions for the game and teams. They can remind players of the rules of the game.

7.2.4 How to play

Initial phase:

1. Decide on the number of Jury members. There must be an odd number of Jury members. Guidelines: If there are only 5 players, then there is one Jury member who takes all the Jury role cards. If there are 9+ players, then there can be 3 Jury members. Choose the appropriate number of Jury member cards for the number of players and shuffle with blank “player” cards.
2. Split the players into Green or Blue teams. Select an equal number of Green and Blue team cards and shuffle. Each player chooses a card to decide teams.
3. The Jury selects a scenario from the list of existing scenarios to set the scene. See Definitions sheet if needed.

Turn phase:

1. Green team players go first to draw a requirements card. They then have 5min to read the information related to the requirements card and 5min to build a strategy to address requirements. The cards have prompts that players should answer, and players can approach it more technically or socially (based on presentation and confidence), as long as they try to win over the Jury.

IMPORTANT: some requirements cards only apply to one scenario, the correspondence is stated in the Information Table. Draw again if the requirements card is for the other scenario.

2. Blue team players against the company take notes on the Green team’s strategy and can ask questions from the Green team for 5min. Then they have to build an adversarial strategy in 5min. They should review the requirement card’s prompt and see how they can attack the Green team’s strategy for fulfilling that requirement. Did they fulfil the requirement? Are there holes in their strategy that do not completely address the prompt? This can be more about the content, the presentation, even ad hominem attacks on the other team, as long as they try to win over the Jury.
3. The Jury has 2min to deliberate and chooses a winner, then explains why for up to 3 minutes. A decision is subjective, but as long as it is explained their ruling is the final word. They may award the point to the most persuasive, confident team or the team with a solid, technical answer. They keep track of the score.

That completes one round of the game.

If playing a second round, for the second round players may change roles. Repeat any of the initialization phase required to create new teams or Jury members.

Then, the Green turn begins, followed by the Blue, then the Jury.

Win conditions

There can be several win conditions based on the time of play.

- One round: short ~30min game where the team who receives the Jury vote wins
- Three rounds: longer ~90min game where the team who receives 3 Jury votes wins

7.2.5 Scenarios

- Toomtoom is a medium-sized marketplace company that is trying to gain a larger foothold in the market. They follow current trends for data security (ISO standards), AI for showing personalized ads, and informed consent that use dark patterns to get more customers. While it is a grey area for being legally compliant given that everyone follows the same dark patterns (like where it is more clicks to refuse consent than give consent) they are considering building brand loyalty by positioning themselves as an extremely trustworthy and transparent company. Toomtoom now seeks to understand if this public trust can be built with dark patterns or if it is worth putting in extra effort to get rid of dark patterns.
- Hoogle Inc., a leading technology company, has implemented a machine learning algorithm for its hiring process. The algorithm, designed to identify the most suitable candidates, inadvertently leads to the hiring of significantly more women than men. This outcome arises because the algorithm heavily weighs a particular feature, "collaborative skills," which, due to various social and educational factors, is more commonly exhibited in the profiles of female candidates. This has led to a disproportionate hiring of women over men, even though the protected attribute (sex) was not used to train the hiring system. Hoogle Inc. now seeks to understand whether their perceived public trust will be affected by this practice and guidance on their next steps.

7.2.6 Scenario's Definitions

Toomtoom definitions:

Dark Pattern – A dark pattern is a way something can be purposefully designed to trick users into doing things, such as buying a hotel room because there is a ticking timer, or having a colourful button to give cookie consent that is more eye-catching than the button to refuse consent.

ISO standard- These are security standards and protocols set by the International Organization for Standardization which has expert representatives from a wide range of member countries.

AI- Stands for artificial intelligence, in which a machine or algorithm is designed to perform high level tasks, such as recognizing someone's interests and serving advertisements relevant to them.

Hoogle Inc. Definitions:

Algorithmic Fairness – Group similarity in outcomes based on a protected attribute.

Biases – Deviations from group similarity in outcome.

Direct Discrimination - Direct discrimination occurs where one person is treated less favourably on grounds of prohibited criterion (racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age, sexual orientation or sex) than another is, has been or would be treated in a comparable situation.

Indirect Discrimination - Indirect discrimination takes place when a neutral provision, criterion, or practice results in a disparate impact on a protected group, unless that provision, criterion or practice is objectively justified by a legitimate aim and the means of achieving that aim are appropriate and necessary.

7.2.7 Information Table (refer to your requirements card)

<u>Scenario</u>	<u>Requirement Card</u>	<u>Information</u>
Hogle	Fairness Through Unawareness	Art. 21 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights; Art. 1-7 of Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation. (both printed-out and highlighted for ease)
Hogle	Fairness Through Awareness	Essentially, fairness through awareness is the use of the protected attribute to constrain the outcomes of the automated system in line with group similarity in outcome. In the Hogle scenario, doing so would produce a trade-off between accuracy and fairness. (key slides on FTA will be shared in the packet from: https://course.ece.cmu.edu/~ece734/fall2013/lectures/cmu13-fairness.pdf)
Hogle	Feature Audit	Once the outputs of the hiring systems are audited, since they have identified the disparity in outcomes between sexes, the weighting of features responsible for such disparities might be reconsidered.
Hogle	Fairness	Associations/correlations between two or more variables may encode the value/information about another variable. Thus, ensuring full independence between variables is a hard task. Plus, those correlations may even be used to run effective attacks against some privacy-enhancing techniques such as differential privacy.
Hogle	Privacy Vs fairness	Many fairness techniques oblige/constrain models to learn from groups of data that were originally discriminated against. Forcing models to learn from insufficient poorly represented groups of data leads models to memorise those data points to achieve the goal of performing well in these groups, however, this memorisation can be exploited by attackers to easily reveal those data points since models memorise them thus their extraction is easier. This problem makes these under-represented groups face a disproportioned risk of leakage.
Toomtoom	Privacy against other users	Users of recommendation systems may use the recommenders' outputs to maintain leakage attacks that can reconstruct or even reveal the data of certain other users whose data were used to train or update these recommendation systems (recommendation systems are periodically updated and retrained to ensure their quality).
Both	Privacy	When training big and large models the companies may use third-party servers such as Amazon sageMaker to train these models due to the need to have big computational resources. Thus, training data needs to be sent to these servers. The servers will then retain full copies of the training data with no technical guarantees that these data won't be used for other purposes and no means to audit these third parties about the usage of the datasets that they retain on their servers after training.

Both	Security Threats	Before deciding to apply any security of privacy solution, engineers and managers should build threat models enumerating all the parties involved in the data flow, the threatening parties and the protected ones, the available resources and desired outcomes. These threat models are the way to check whether a given security strategy succeeds or not in meeting the requirements of these threat models.
Both	Training	Companies and projects have multidisciplinary teams working on them; thus, each team comes with a different background of knowledge. This diversity makes the training for aspects of privacy, transparency and other requirements challenging for all teams.
Both	Communication is Blind	There is lots of research about how little privacy policies describing data processing are read, given that they can be long, vague, and not written for a general audience. Most people have probably never read one in their life! A consent form may also try to explain the data processing that consent is needed for, but it can be difficult to explain the purpose and research also shows that many people do not often have the background to weigh the risks and benefits, but make decisions based on expectations of privacy, risks, and benefits.
Both	Jargon or Overkill?	Even if someone wants to read a privacy policy or consent form to understand how data is processed, often it can be written legalese to cover legal requirements. While it may be approved by a lawyer, the terms can be confusing. They may use lots of vague terms to cover many scenarios, but then it is unclear what is happening. Additionally, policies may be endless and full of technical jargon e.g., a 50+ long list of companies that will be sent your data, or details about how it will be used for a specific type of machine learning algorithm to improve services that someone would only understand with training.
Toomtoom	Legal Manipulation	<p>The Digital Services Act (DSA) is an EU regulation that states providers of online platforms (such as online marketplaces, app stores, collaborative economy platforms and social media platforms). They give examples such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - giving unequal visual prominence to any options when asking the user for a decision (a form of misdirection technique); - repetitively requesting or urging the receipting to make a decision such as repeatedly requesting consents to data processing where consent has previously been refused (especially in the form of a pop-up that interferes with the user experience) or has been refused through the use of automatic refusal configurations; <p>However, in practice this can be hard to implement, as there are very few “neutral” designs.</p> <p>Following a regulation, the enforcement of any violations is paramount. This will set a precedence. However, the regulation is very new, and no public decisions have yet to be made. Thus, many dark patterns may still be in a grey area until a case is brought up in court.</p>

7.2.8 Cards

Funded by the European Union

Requirement cards

Privacy against other users

How to protect against malicious users of who can reconstruct the data of other users whose data were used to train/update the recommendation system?

Privacy Vs fairness

Constraining ML algorithms to be fair obliges the algorithms to learn from **minorities** in the data exposing them to higher risks of leakage. How can that be addressed?

Fairness

Sensitive features such as race, gender, and age may be encoded in correlations between other insensitive features. How to ensure that the elimination of some sensitive features is successful ?

Fairness Through Awareness

Should Hoogle curate the dataset to achieve demographic parity (or a fairness metric of your choosing) in the outcomes of the hiring system at the cost of making the sample unrepresentative?

Feature Audit

Should the "collaborative skills" feature be reexamined since it may remove the disparate impact?

Fairness Through Unawareness

Should Hoogle continue to rely on their approach of not including the protected attribute as a feature?

Legal Manipulation?

How is the current design of consent using dark patterns justified or not? Would it be legal?

Training

Privacy concerns require adequate training to understand what is important to communicate. What kind of training is offered?

Legalese or Overkill?

How is relevant information conveyed to stakeholders considering the tradeoff between specificity and legal generality?

Communication is Blind

How are the stakeholders informed about the data processing (e.g., AI, dark patterns) practices given how difficult it is to communicate?

Privacy

The building of models in third party servers includes leaving copies of data that are personal in those servers. How can such a risk be addressed?

Security Threats

The quality of the security measures should be assessed based on how well they address the threat models. What is the best strategy to design a performant threat model ?

Funded by the European Union

Instructions

Role play game

Welcome!

In the CR2 role play game where multiple teams are given a fictional scenario. The goal is to discuss elements of trust and transparency in data processing in complex social, legal, and technical situations with two teams competing against each other.

Instructions

The Jury chooses a scenario to set the stage.

The Green team chooses a requirement card and builds a strategy to fulfill it. The Blue team takes notes and argues against the Green team. At the end of each round the Jury chooses a winner. *See instructions for different win conditions.*

Mini Instruction Cards

Green team

You go first to draw a requirements card. You have 5min to read the related information and answer the requirements card in another 5min .

Blue team

Take notes on the Green team's strategy. You go second. 5min to question the Green team and build an adversarial strategy in 5min.

Jury Deliberation

5min for the jury to deliberate and choose a winner, with clear reasoning of why.

Jury and Player Cards

Jury Member

Congrats! You are on the Jury. You will be judging the Green and Blue team strategies.

Player

Congrats! You are a player. You will be coming up with strategies to win over the Jury.

**scenario cards: see Definitions
sheet for more detail**

Dark or Light?

Toomtoom is a medium-sized marketing company that is trying to gain a larger foothold in the market. They follow current trends for data privacy, security (ISO standards), AI for showing personalized ads, and informed consent that use dark patterns to get more customers. While it is a gray area for being legally compliant given that everyone follows the same dark patterns, they are considering building brand loyalty by positioning themselves as an extremely trustworthy and transparent company. Toomtoom now seeks to understand if this public trust can be built with dark patterns or if it is worth putting in extra effort to use other methods.

Hired or Fired?

Hoggle Inc., a leading tech company, has implemented a machine learning algorithm for hiring. The algorithm, designed to identify the most suitable candidates, leads to the hiring of significantly more women than men. The algorithm heavily weighs "collaborative skills," which, due to various social and educational factors, is more common the profiles of female candidates. This has led to a disproportionate hiring of women over men, even though the sensitive attribute was not used to train the hiring system. Hoggle Inc. now seeks to understand whether their perceived public trust will be affected by this practice and guidance on their next steps.

The material composing the full board game kit, including those that are not displayed here, are publicly available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number [10.5281/zenodo.17242424](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17242424).⁶

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17242424>

7.3 Annex III: Crossroad 3's game

7.3.1 Game instructions

Number of Players: Ideally 5 individual players- 4 players and 1 game master.

Intended Audience: General public with basic interest in online privacy and security wishing to learn more about data rights. Skills required are reasoning, affinity building and debating.

Timing and duration: One round takes around 16 minutes. The game provides enough material to play 21 rounds, but players can opt for a shorter version of the game by not playing all the cards.

Components

Mission: A legal and/or technical challenge on online privacy and security that ordinary people can possibly face in real life. The missions come in a set of cards (21 in total) and players aim to make a convincing argument on how to handle and solve them to earn points.

Skill cards: These cards complement the Mission cards as they provide useful info about the relevant legislation or technical protocol. They assist the players in solving the Mission at stake. There are 8 skill cards for each Mission.

Board: Functions to add motivational drives to the game as well as further challenges towards the end. There's a colored box for each round to be played and some boxes offer the possibility of earning double points, skipping the mission which results in loss of points and towards the end, the challenge of less time to solve the Mission is introduced as players will have gained practice by then.

Score Chart: It keeps track of points earned during the game.

Correct Answers Sheet: Provides an accurate solution to each Mission. The Game Master relies on this sheet to give points to the players.

Glossary

Game Master: The Game Master draws the Mission cards from the deck, distributes the skill cards to players, keeps the time during game, checks the correct answers sheet and gives points to the players according to the accuracy of the solution they come up with for each Mission. They also fill in the Score Chart and make sure that the players comply with the game rules.

Trophies: Recognition or award for an outstanding result achieved. The trophies are awarded at the end of the game. Any player scoring 450 points and higher gets a gold trophy. Any player scoring 350 points and higher gets a silver trophy. Any player scoring 300 points and higher gets a bronze trophy. These score thresholds are for those who play all the cards (21 rounds).

Game Setup

1. Place the board on the table and place the two decks of cards in the middle: **Missions** and **Skill cards**. Each Mission is numbered and comes with a corresponding set of **eight skill cards**. Check the board to see if that round has specific incentives or challenges such as double points, option of skipping the mission or less time to play. Each round is represented by a colored box on the board.

2. The Game Master draws a Mission card and places it on the table revealing the content or reading it aloud. She then distributes the complementary skill cards to the players (**2 skill cards per player**). The skill cards are to be viewed only by the players who possess them.
3. The players get 6 minutes to reflect on how to handle and solve the mission with support from the skill cards. The Game Master keeps the time.
4. Once the time is up, each player makes an argument on how to handle and solve the challenge at stake (Mission). They each have 2 minutes to do that unless the board displays '1 minute less' for that round. Make sure to check the board for each round. Again, the Game Master keeps the time.
5. Players **give a point out of 5 to each other** at the end of each round depending on how convincing and impressive the argument was. The **Game Master gives a point out of 10 to each player** at the end of each round depending on the accuracy of the solution they come up with. The Game Master relies on the Answers Sheet to determine accuracy.
6. The Game Master adds the points to the Score Chart and then starts the next round.

Game Premise and Goals

Players get points from their fellow players by making a convincing and impressive argument. This depends on their skills of reasoning, affinity building, debating and making connections. Players are assisted by the Skill Cards in the game which provide useful info relevant to the Mission to be tackled. Players also get points from the Game Master depending on the accuracy of the solution they come up with. The player who scores the most points in total wins the game. On top of that, any player scoring 450 and higher gets a gold trophy. Any player scoring 350 and higher gets a silver trophy. Any player scoring 300 and higher gets a bronze trophy at the end of the game.

Game Rules:

- Players are not allowed to reach for information other than the one that is already provided by the Skill card.
- Players don't reveal their Skill cards to other players.
- Players are not allowed to view the Answers Sheet till the end of the game. It is only for the Game Master's usage during the game.
- Players need to comply with the time restrictions.
- Players are supposed to think and read silently during the 6-minute reflection time.
- When the board offers the option of skipping the Mission (not playing) for a particular round, any player who skips the Mission loses 10 points.
- When the board offers double points for a particular round, each player's total point for that round (points from the GM + points from the fellow players) is multiplied with 2.
- When the board displays '1 minute less' for a particular round, the players have 1 minute less time of reflection and 1 minute less time of presenting their argument.

The game provides enough material to play 21 rounds, but players can opt for a shorter version of the game by not playing all the cards. In that case, it is advised that they decide on the point thresholds for winning trophies before starting the game.

7.3.2 Game board

7.3.3 Cards

SynergyLegal: Legal and Technical Challenges around Data Rights

**Missions and
Complementary Skill
Cards**

SynergyLegal

Mission 1

As a regular customer of an online retailer, you've always trusted the company with your personal information. However, you recently received an email notification that there was a data breach, and your sensitive details like your name and address have been exposed. This news is worrisome, and you're now concerned about the safety of your identity and finances. What should the company do in response to a data breach?

SynergyLegal: Legal and Technical Challenges around Data Rights

Skill 1

Right to be Informed: Upon experiencing a data breach, the company has a legal obligation to inform affected customers without undue delay. This right to be informed ensures that individuals are promptly notified about the breach, the type of data compromised, and the potential risks to their privacy and security.

Skill 1

Right to Access: Individuals have the right to access their personal data held by the company, including the data affected by the breach. This right enables individuals to review the compromised information and understand the scope of the breach.

Skill 1

Right to Rectification: Individuals have the right to rectify inaccurate or incomplete personal data. This right allows individuals to address any errors or inconsistencies in their data that may have arisen due to the breach.

Skill 1

Right to Erasure: Individuals have the right to request the erasure of their personal data when it is no longer necessary for the purpose for which it was collected. This right empowers individuals to control the retention of their data and minimize the potential for future misuse.

These are just a few examples of the cards. All the material composing the full board game kit are available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number [10.5281/zenodo.10395154](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10395154).⁷

⁷<https://zenodo.org/records/10395155?>

7.3.4 Score chart

SYNERGYLEGAL SCORE CHART				
	PLAYER 1 Name:	PLAYER 2 Name:	PLAYER 3 Name:	PLAYER 4 Name:
ROUND 1				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 2				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 3				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 4				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 5				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 6				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 7				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 8				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 9				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 10				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 11				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 12				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 13				
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ROUND 14				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 15				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 16				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 17				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 18				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 19				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 20				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
ROUND 21				
Points from GM				
+ Fellows				
TOTAL				

*GM stands for Game Master, and Fellows stands for fellow players.

7.3.5 Correct answers sheet

Mission 01 There are key obligations and procedures for companies in the event of a data breach, as specified by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Within 72 hours of awareness, retailers must notify the supervisory authority, unless the breach poses low risk. Transparency is crucial, requiring clear communication with affected individuals about breach details. Risk assessment and mitigation measures are mandated, with the involvement of a Data Protection Officer if available. The primary role of the data protection officer (DPO) is to ensure that her organization processes the personal data of its staff, customers, providers, or any other individuals (also referred to as data subjects) in compliance with the applicable data protection rules. Thorough documentation is required, encompassing breach specifics and actions taken. Affected individuals possess rights including information access, data rectification, erasure, processing restriction, data portability, and the right to lodge complaints with supervisory authorities.

Mission 02 To navigate the intersection of GDPR compliance and delivering a personalized online shopping experience, e-commerce companies should adopt a strategic approach. Key strategies include practicing data minimization by collecting only essential personal data, ensuring transparency by informing customers about data usage and processing purposes and providing customers with control over their data through access and management options. Adhering to purpose limitation principles, implementing robust data security measures, and setting clear data retention policies are crucial. In the event of a data breach, prompt notification to affected individuals is essential. Vendor management should prioritize selecting partners with adequate data protection measures, and incorporating data protection into the design of systems is vital. Regular reviews and compliance assessments ensure ongoing alignment with GDPR principles.

Mission 03 For small business owners utilizing cloud services, ensuring GDPR compliance and safeguarding company information involves strategic considerations. Key strategies include understanding the shared responsibility model with cloud providers, clearly defining data ownership and control in service agreements, and implementing robust data encryption measures. Access control and authentication, data loss prevention, and regular security audits are crucial for minimizing risks. Careful evaluation of cloud providers, consideration of data residency requirements, and establishment of data processing agreements with third parties are essential. Additionally, having a comprehensive data breach notification plan in place is crucial to meet GDPR requirements. Implementing these strategies helps small businesses address data ownership and security concerns, ensuring compliance with GDPR and protecting their valuable information.

Mission 04 Achieving a balance between data utilization and citizen privacy in smart cities requires a comprehensive approach focusing on transparency, accountability, and citizen empowerment. Key strategies include transparent data practices with informed consent, data minimization, and purpose limitation. Citizens should have control over their data through access, rectification, and erasure rights, as well as the ability to port their data. Robust data security measures and breach notification plans are crucial. Involving citizens in decision-making processes, anonymizing or pseudonymizing data, and integrating data protection into smart city design is essential. Regular reviews, independent oversight, and accountability mechanisms ensure alignment with GDPR principles and build trust in the smart city ecosystem.

Mission 05 To foster a robust cybersecurity culture in a global financial services company, a comprehensive approach is essential. Key strategies include obtaining executive leadership commitment, conducting risk assessments for targeted cybersecurity initiatives, and implementing mandatory awareness training for all employees. Tailored, role-based training programs should address specific risks associated with different roles. Consideration of cultural and language factors in localized training, incorporation of gamification and incentives, and continuous communication are crucial. Establishing a cybersecurity champion program and conducting simulated phishing exercises enhance employee engagement and awareness. Regular assessments of the cybersecurity culture ensure ongoing effectiveness and identify areas for improvement.

Mission 06 For small business owners utilizing cloud services, ensuring GDPR compliance and safeguarding company information involves strategic considerations. Key strategies include understanding the shared responsibility model with cloud providers, clearly defining data ownership and control in service agreements, and implementing robust data encryption measures. Access control and authentication, data loss prevention, and regular security audits are crucial for minimizing risks. Careful evaluation of cloud providers, consideration of data residency requirements, and establishment of data processing agreements with third parties are essential. Additionally, having a comprehensive data breach notification plan in place is crucial to meet GDPR requirements. Implementing these strategies helps small businesses address data ownership and security concerns, ensuring compliance with GDPR and protecting their valuable information.

Mission 07 FinBank's unauthorized sale of customer financial information constitutes a breach of privacy and GDPR regulations. To regain trust and comply with GDPR, FinBank must immediately cease data sharing, be transparent about the issue, and notify affected customers. Obtaining explicit consent and implementing an opt-in mechanism for data sharing is essential. Adhering to data minimization, purpose limitation, and implementing robust data security measures are crucial. Customers should have control over their data, and FinBank may need to appoint a Data Protection Officer for oversight. In the event of a breach, prompt notification to affected individuals and supervisory authorities is required. Employee training on GDPR compliance, fostering a culture of data privacy, and regular reviews to ensure alignment with GDPR principles are necessary steps for FinBank's commitment to safeguarding customer financial information.

Mission 08 To protect your child's privacy on the online gaming platform GameVerse, take the following steps: carefully review GameVerse's privacy policy, seek clear and accessible consent for data collection, explore options to restrict data collection if needed, monitor in-app purchases and advertising settings, educate your child about online privacy risks, communicate concerns with GameVerse's customer support or data protection officer, consider alternative gaming platforms with stronger privacy protections, and, if

necessary, report privacy violations to the relevant data protection authority for investigation and enforcement of data protection laws.

Mission 09 In response to the KidLearn data breach, take immediate action to secure your child's account by changing passwords and logging out, and consider deleting the account to prevent further exposure. Contact KidLearn to understand the breach's extent, inquire about exposed data, and request details on preventive measures. Monitor your child's credit and consider legal action, consulting an attorney if needed. Report the breach to data protection authorities, raise awareness among parents, and demand accountability from KidLearn, urging robust security measures and transparent privacy policies. Additionally, support initiatives for stronger data protection legislation, particularly for children's online services, emphasizing data minimization and parental control.

Mission 10 XYZ Manufacturing aims to harness scattered data for enhanced production efficiency and cost reduction through a multifaceted approach. Strategies encompass the integration and harmonization of data into a centralized repository for comprehensive analysis. Cleaning and preprocessing ensure data quality, leading to accurate insights. The use of analytics and visualization tools uncovers valuable patterns and trends, optimizing production processes and minimizing waste. Data governance policies assure quality, consistency, and security, aligning with privacy regulations. Collaboration and knowledge sharing among data scientists, engineers, and production personnel enable informed decision-making and continuous improvement. Investment in scalable data infrastructure and analytics talent supports data-driven initiatives, fostering innovation and experimentation. Real-time data monitoring and predictive analytics enhance proactive intervention and maintenance optimization. Embracing a culture of continuous improvement ensures the effectiveness of data-driven strategies, maximizing value and reducing costs over time.

Mission 11 FitLife can enhance its personalized fitness recommendations from wearable devices by implementing various strategies. First, comprehensive data collection and aggregation from all devices create a centralized repository for holistic analysis. Cleaning and preprocessing ensure data quality, enhancing accuracy. User segmentation based on fitness goals and characteristics informs detailed user profiles. Advanced machine learning algorithms identify patterns for tailored recommendations. Real-time data analysis offers immediate feedback on fitness progress. Adaptive recommendations evolve with user progress and changing goals. Transparent AI techniques build user trust through clear explanations of data usage. Robust data security measures protect sensitive information and comply with privacy regulations. A feedback mechanism encourages user engagement and continuous improvement. Collaboration with fitness experts ensures recommendations align with evidence-based practices, validating accuracy and effectiveness.

Mission 12 To effectively manage and safeguard the substantial data from connected devices, the city can employ a set of strategies. Establishing a robust data governance framework and privacy policy ensures clear guidelines on data ownership, collection practices, and sharing protocols. Integrating data from various sources into a centralized repository with standardized formats facilitates seamless analysis. Anonymizing or pseudonymizing personal data reduces identification risks while preserving individual privacy. Adhering to purpose limitation and data minimization principles involves collecting only essential personal data for specific urban issues. Implementing access controls and obtaining explicit user consent ensures data security

and privacy. Robust security measures and a data breach notification plan protect against unauthorized access, with encryption and regular audits. Upholding data subject rights involves providing mechanisms for individuals to access, rectify, or erase their data. Transparency and accountability are achieved through clear communication and oversight mechanisms. Purpose-specific data analysis and regular reviews ensure compliance and continuous improvement in data handling practices.

Mission 13 To enhance patient care, minimize readmissions, and personalize treatment plans, Zenith Health can adopt several key strategies for handling and analyzing diverse health data from connected devices. Establishing a centralized data repository will consolidate information from various sources, creating a comprehensive patient health profile. Standardizing and harmonizing data formats ensure compatibility and accuracy, while robust data quality management procedures maintain the completeness and consistency of aggregated health data. Implementing a comprehensive data governance framework and privacy policy ensures responsible data usage and protection. Advanced analytics and machine learning techniques can extract meaningful insights, identifying risk factors and personalizing treatment plans. Predictive analytics helps in developing models to identify high-risk patients and provide targeted interventions. Tailoring treatment plans based on individual health profiles, real-time data monitoring, patient engagement, and continuous improvement through feedback and insights contribute to the overall effectiveness of Zenith Health's data-driven initiatives.

Mission 14 In response to the data breach aftermath, Genewise should take immediate and transparent actions to rebuild user trust. This involves promptly notifying affected users, securing compromised data, and conducting a thorough investigation to identify and address vulnerabilities. Offering credit monitoring and identity protection services can help mitigate risks for users. Implementing enhanced data security measures, improving communication, and expressing a sincere apology are crucial steps. Actively seeking user feedback, initiating trust-building initiatives, and providing comprehensive data protection training to employees demonstrate a commitment to privacy. Regular security assessments, updating privacy policies, and implementing user-friendly mechanisms to exercise data rights are essential for rebuilding user confidence in Genewise's commitment to data privacy and security.

Mission 15 To address concerns about user privacy and informed consent, HealthTrack should implement a comprehensive strategy. This involves obtaining explicit and informed consent from users before sharing their data with third parties, offering granular control over data sharing preferences, and ensuring transparency about data usage. The company should consider anonymizing or pseudonymizing data for research purposes to protect individual privacy. Robust data security measures, the right for users to withdraw consent, and adherence to data subject rights are crucial components. Appointing a Data Protection Officer, conducting regular reviews, and educating users about data privacy risks contribute to a holistic approach. HealthTrack's commitment to user trust can be reinforced through clear communication, continuous compliance assessments, and empowering users with the knowledge to make informed decisions about their data sharing preferences.

Mission 16 To ensure the privacy and security of patient data in its Electronic Health Record (EHR) system, Global Health Systems should implement a comprehensive set of strategies. This includes establishing robust access controls and role-based authorization to limit data access based on user roles. Implementing multi-

factor authentication adds an extra layer of security. The incorporation of audit trails and access logging provides a detailed record of user activity. Techniques like data masking and encryption protect sensitive patient information during access and transmission. Regular security audits and vulnerability assessments help identify and address potential weaknesses. Comprehensive data privacy training for all system users is essential, along with an incident response plan for effective management of data breaches. Compliance with data protection regulations, regular policy updates, and continuous monitoring for improvements ensure that Global Health Systems maintains a high standard of data protection for patient information.

Mission 17 To address concerns about user privacy and informed consent in data sharing practices, HealthTrack, the wearable device company, can adopt a comprehensive strategy. This includes obtaining explicit and informed consent from users before sharing their data, granting users granular control over data sharing preferences, and ensuring transparency about data usage. The company should consider anonymizing or pseudonymizing user data for research purposes, implement robust data security measures, and allow users to withdraw consent at any time. Ensuring users' rights to access, review, rectify, or erase their personal data is crucial, and appointing a Data Protection Officer (DPO) can oversee compliance. Regular reviews and compliance assessments should be conducted, and user education and awareness initiatives should be implemented to inform users about data privacy importance. Overall, these measures aim to demonstrate HealthTrack's commitment to user privacy, protect sensitive data, and build trust among its user base.

Mission 18 To securely and legally handle sensitive health data, MediCare should implement a multifaceted approach. This includes robust data security measures involving encryption, access controls, and regular audits to protect patient data from unauthorized access. Data minimization and purpose limitation principles should be applied to collect only essential health data, avoiding unnecessary information. Enforcing strict access controls and role-based authorization ensures that users have the minimum necessary access. Establishing a clear data breach notification plan and incident response strategy is crucial to promptly address and contain any security breaches. Patient consent should be obtained before sharing health data with third parties, with transparent communication about the purposes, recipients, and privacy measures. Respecting patients' data rights, implementing a comprehensive data governance framework, and regular reviews of data handling practices contribute to legal compliance. Additionally, employee training and awareness programs are vital to educate staff about their responsibilities in handling sensitive patient data and the significance of data security measures within the organization.

Mission 19 To halt the use of your personal data and medical records by ResearchHub for research purposes, follow these steps: Firstly, formally notify ResearchHub in writing of your decision to withdraw consent for specific research projects, specifying the projects and providing necessary personal details. Secondly, request the deletion of any data related to the projects you've opted out of, emphasizing your right to data erasure and setting a deadline for compliance. Maintain a documented record of all communications with ResearchHub for potential follow-ups. If compliance issues persist, consult with a legal professional specializing in data privacy and intellectual property for advice on potential courses of action. Additionally, if needed, report ResearchHub to the relevant data protection authority, which can investigate and enforce compliance. Share your experience with others involved in medical research studies, advocating for informed consent and data control. Overall, these actions affirm your right to withdraw consent and safeguard your personal information effectively.

Mission 20 To effectively address data control concerns in collaborative research, ResearchCentral can implement several key strategies. Firstly, establish a robust data governance framework, defining ownership, access, and sharing rights. Develop project-specific Data Management Plans (DMPs) outlining data collection, storage, and sharing procedures. Implement clear and enforceable data sharing agreements among collaborators, specifying terms and intellectual property rights. Form a Data Access Committee (DAC) to review and approve data access requests, ensuring compliance and privacy protection. Create a secure data repository, employing strong security measures, and encourage proper data citation practices. Provide researchers with comprehensive data literacy training and continuously monitor practices for compliance. Foster transparency and open communication among stakeholders, promoting a culture of responsible data sharing within ResearchCentral. These measures collectively enhance data management, protect privacy, and facilitate collaborative research endeavors.

Mission 21 To enhance the company's data handling practices and prioritize children's privacy, the data protection specialist should implement a series of focused actions. These include adopting a data minimization principle, collecting only essential data for legitimate purposes. The privacy policies should be simplified and presented in plain language for parents and children to easily understand. Obtaining explicit and informed consent from parents before data collection is crucial, with clear explanations of the purposes and data types involved. Anonymization or pseudonymization of children's data for research purposes is recommended for privacy preservation. The company should provide parents with accessible tools to manage and control their children's data, ensuring transparency. Robust security measures, including encryption and regular audits, are essential to prevent unauthorized access. Conducting Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) for high-risk activities and providing comprehensive data privacy training to all employees are crucial steps. Regular reviews, updates, and collaboration with child protection experts will further strengthen the company commitment to children's privacy.

7.3.6 Printing instructions

Printing Instructions

1. Download the Game File:

- Start by downloading the printable game files.
- All the game files are in a high-quality PDF format. What's included are the Board, Mission Cards, Skill Cards, Score Chart, Correct Answers Sheet and Game Instructions.

2. Check Printer Compatibility:

- Verify that your printer supports the required paper for the game.
- We recommend using cardstock paper for printing the game but regular matte paper would also work. The paper size for all card files is A4. You will need scissors to cut out the cards after printing. The paper size for the board is 350mm x 334mm (A2).

3. Open the File:

- Locate the downloaded game files on your computer.
- Double-click to open the files using the appropriate software (Adobe Reader, image viewer, etc.)

4. Print:

- Access the print settings either from the file menu or by pressing Ctrl + P (Windows) or Command + P (Mac).
- Adjust print settings for a horizontal orientation, A4 paper size, and high quality before printing the Mission Cards and the Skill Cards.
- Adjust print settings for a vertical orientation, A4 paper size before printing the Correct Answers Sheet, Game Instructions and Score Chart.
- Adjust print settings for a horizontal orientation, A2 paper size before printing the Board.

7. Allow to Dry:

- If using an inkjet printer, allow the printed pages to dry completely before handling to prevent smudging.

9. Cut or Assemble:

- Cut out each card with scissors.

- Separate the types of cards by Missions and Skills by number. All the material composing the full board game kit are available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number [10.5281/zenodo.17243159](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17243159)⁸

⁸<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17243159>

7.4.2 Instructions

PRIVACYLANDIA
GAME INSTRUCTIONS

INTRODUCTION

This is a role-based game where different players take the role of the inhabitants of a fictional town. Each player needs to collaborate with at least another player and uses her/his knowledge in legal and technological domains to solve problems which an individual being data subject may face in real life.

PLAYERS

At least 6 participants to be grouped into teams of minimum 2 players; the game is recommended for scholars, professionals, and students with expertise in law and/or technological fields.

THE BOARD

A3 (210 x 297 mm) color printed playground with different paths and challenges.

ACCESSORIES

- 1 dice
- 6 pawns
- 6 printed role cards
- printed (50,5 x 83,5 mm) challenge cards: Tier 1 (Green), Tier 2 (Blue), Tier 3 (Red),
- printed bonus cards: Tier 1 (120 x 62 mm), Tier 2 (127 x 67 mm), Tier 3 (140 x 77 mm)
- printed penalty cards: 110 x 80 mm

DURATION

Recommended time is 1 hour, unless none of the teams reaches the FINISH before time lapse. In that case, the ranking will be done based on the points collected by each team up to that point.

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TEAM CONSTRUCTION

TEAMS

Each player should declare from the beginning the team he/she would like to form/join. Each team contains minimum 2 members (one with legal and one with technical expertise).

The team members may collaborate with each other during the game. Points collected by each member are summed up in the final ranking that will decide the winning team. The goal of the game is not simply reaching the FINISH first but collecting the most points possible. Team members may solve all the challenges together and hence gain more points – difficult challenges may assign bonuses to each member of the team.

PERSONAS:

Before starting the game, each player selects a role card (“Persona”) that will be attributed to them during the whole game. Each persona has certain characteristics and skills related to certain fields on the game or certain challenges. Personas bring two types of advantages: field advantage (when a player stops on the field which corresponds with their persona gets a bonus) and expertise advantage (when a player solves the challenge question which corresponds with their persona gets a bonus).

Persona	Field Advantage	Expertise advantage
Doctor	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Hospital and Pharmacy field	+1 extra point for any challenge solved.
Lawyer	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Court and Police Station field	+1 extra point for any IT-related challenge solved.
Researcher	1 extra point if he/she stops in the University and Library field	+1 extra point for any RED challenge solved.
IT developer	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Internet provider, Telecom provider and Digital Platform field	+1 extra point for any legal-related challenge solved.
Student	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Social Network, Streaming Service and Gym field	+1 extra point for any GREEN challenge solved
Entrepreneur	1 extra point if he/she stops in the Bank and Post Office field	+1 extra point for any BLUE challenge solved.

START

The game starts from the START field.

To decide the order, each player will launch the dice; whoever gets the higher number will go first. In the case 2 or more players get 6, they will launch the dice once again until the order is defined.

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GAMEPLAY

The players in turn launches the dice and moves the pawn on the board according to the number on the dice (from 1 to 6).

There is no predefined direction to be followed: it can be played clockwise or counterclockwise.

The game ends when each member of the team reaches the FINISH, hence every player of the team may decide to move in the same or different direction with the other team members.

The goal of the game is to reach the FINISH with the highest points possible.

There are different LOCATION FIELDS, ACTIONS FIELDS and CHALLENGES in the path (inspired from real-world scenarios) which require a certain action. This may influence the "community" as a whole or one specific player/team.

The challenges will have different levels of difficulties (Green – Low, Blue – Medium, and Red – High) and might involve other entities as well.

When the player is positioned in a challenge field, he/she will randomly extract one card of the same color from the deck of challenge cards.

The player will read the challenge described in the card to the community.

The "solution" to the challenge may be first discussed within the team or directly presented to the community and its outcome is evaluated by the other players. If the other players are satisfied with the proposed solution, the player (and his/her team members in some cases) will gain the specified bonus that can be used later in the game or given to another player/team member at any time or when he/she is asking for support. If one or more players are not satisfied with the proposed solution, they need to provide an explanation for their disagreement, and may suggest / recommend some elements that should have been included / discussed as part of the solution.

Other team members may decide to intervene/help solve the challenge or decide not to be involved.

If the majority of the other players (community) decide the solution is not satisfactory, the player (and his/her team on some occasions) will gain a penalty (based on the difficulty level of the challenge).

If a player is never engaged in discussions around the challenges (e.g., does not express his/her approval of or disagreement with the proposed solution, does not volunteer to help his/her team members, etc., he/she will be penalized by the other players. Again, the penalty will be decided by the community. The goal of the game is to promote collaboration and engage as much as possible, not to be indifferent.

TRANSITION: The orange wall dividing the two levels cannot be passed - must reach the TRANSIT cell and PAY the specified number of points to second level.

LOCATION FIELDS:

- Bank
- Clothing store
- Coffee shop
- Court
- eShop
- Digital platform
- Gym
- Hospital
- Internet provider
- Library
- Pharmacy
- Police station
- Market
- Municipality
- Social Network
- Streaming service
- Telecom provider
- University

ACTION FIELDS:

- **Reverse direction:** The player must change the direction in the next round.
- **Go back:** The player must move 1 cell backwards.
- **Taxi:** The player can move up to 5 cells proceeding the same direction.
- **Bonus:** The player gets 3 points when reaching this field.
- **Data breach:** The player gets a penalty if he/she reaches this field: 5 points will be deducted.
- **Refund:** The player will get 40% extra points of his/her current balance.
- **Go to start:** The player must start the game from the beginning, without losing the points collected so far.
- **Metro:** The player can go to any field in the next round
- **Roll again:** The player can launch the dice again and hence play a second round.
- **Maxi bonus:** The player will gain 10 extra points that can be used in the next rounds.
- **Personal data infringement penalty:** The player will lose 10 points.

CHALLENGE CARDS:

- GREEN cards - 1 min for the presentation of the solution + 1 min Q&A
- BLUE cards - 2 min for the presentation of the solution + 2 min Q&A
- RED cards - 3 min for the presentation of the solution + 3 min Q&A

BONUS CARDS:

- Tier 1 (Green)**
- Gain 1 point
- Gain a 10% bonus on the current points
- Gain 10% extra on the next bonus from the action fields

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Tier 2 (Blue)

- Gain 2 point
- Gain a 25% bonus on the current points
- Gain 30% extra on the next bonus from the action fields

Tier 3 (Red)

- Gain 3 point (+1 extra point to the team members)
- Gain a 40% bonus on the current points
- Gain 50% extra on the next bonus from the action fields

PENALTY CARDS:

Tier 1 (Green)

- Lose 1 point
- Give 1 point to another player
- Move 1 cell back

Tier 2 (Blue)

- Lose 2 point
- Give 2 points to another player
- Move 3 cells back

Tier 3 (Red)

- Lose 3 point (-1 point to the team members)
- Give 3 points to another player
- Move 5 cells back

For non-engaging players:

- No points awarded in case challenges are solved by another team member
- Skip 1, 2, 3 rounds
- Lose 1, 3, 5 points

7.4.3 Cards

Challenge cards

Tier 1 (Green)

(50,5 x 83,5 mm)

Tier 2 (Blue)

(50,5 x 83,5 mm)

Tier 3 (Red)

(50,5 x 83,5 mm)

Bonus cards

(120 x 62 mm)

(127 x 67 mm)

(140 x 77 mm)

7.4.4 Personas

<p>THE DOCTOR</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>	
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<p>THE LAYWER</p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>	
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These are only a few exemplifying cards. All the material composing the full board game kit are available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number: [10.5281/zenodo.17250821](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17250821).⁹

⁹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17250821>

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7.4.5 Challenges

Tier 1 (Green)

In your opinion, did Brexit influence the GDPR implementation? If yes, how?

You are a researcher organizing genetic data for clinical trials. As you carry on your data wrangling you realize a consent form is missing. How should you proceed?

You are an athlete using a fitness tracking app. The app requests information that is completely unrelated to the service it is providing, after you complete the paid registration. How should you react?

You found out that your (personal) data was used without your consent on a website/product/service. What will be your next step? Will you contact any authority at regional/national/EU level?

You have reached XY website. The company is asking permission to access your location in real time to provide better recommendations closer to you. What are you going to do? Why?

Welcome to XYZ social media. For us to deliver the best services we ask you to provide your consent for sharing your personal data, statistical data and functional data with external providers. What are you going to do? Will you agree or not, why?

You applied to a private healthcare provider located in the EU. When they took down your personal information, they also asked for your phone number and said this information is needed to contact you about your test results and inform you about special campaigns. Would you agree to give them your phone number, why?

You sign up for a research activity after ordering a DNA test to your home. The research is aimed at generating health recommendations based on your exercise and diet data. After a while, you change your mind and want to quit the research, but the company representative says that you cannot quit at this point. Would you agree with the company representative's words, why?

Tier 2 (Blue)

You received your blood count test results after your visit to the hospital, but you noticed they were not your results but someone else's with the same name and surname as you. You contacted the hospital and asked them to correct the mistake, but you have been told that once the test results are finalized, they cannot be amended. Would you agree with the hospital officer's statement, why?

You received an email from an unknown colleague who presumably works in a different department. The mail does not ask for any confidential information, but it does ask to provide information about the software and hardware specifications of your working station. What would you do in that situation? How could you try to verify the identity of the person requesting information?

You are a clinical trial coordinator in a biotechnology startup that processes health data. One of your data analysts suggests that a few patients at a clinical trial your company is carrying out may be at risk of cardiovascular disease, a finding which is unrelated to your service that patients consented for. Should you approach the patients? If so, how?

The provider of a digital service is rolling up slowly the two-factor authentication (2FA) mechanism to increase security and ensure privacy for its users. However, it requires you to provide a mobile phone number to receive a one-time PIN code expiring in a limited time (e.g., 15 seconds). What are you going to do? Will you agree to provide your number and why?

A big tech company has decided to challenge the EC regarding the applicability of the DMA. They believe this regulation doesn't apply to them since their service/platform is not so popular in Europe. What is your opinion on this? Do you believe users should have the right to select pre-installed apps on their devices even though these are provided from external third parties?

When you were in your local pharmacist to collect your medication, the pharmacist offered to give your next-door neighbor's medications who also has a chronic illness. When you asked how the pharmacist knew where you lived, he/she mentioned that it is accessible from the database that they have been using. Do you think that is there something wrong with his/her actions about sharing your neighbor's medical information with you, why?

You are designing a psychology study to be performed on students where you examine the effect of sleep on anxiety. In your form you want to be as comprehensive as possible to design an optimal study and analysis. However, you are aware that the ethics committee may not be lenient with asking questions that are too personal or may be deemed irrelevant to the study, hence you wish to adhere to data minimization. What criteria will you use to decide what risk factors to include in your study?

You are applying for a job and are required to complete a psychometric test. You feel that the questions regarding lifestyle, personal information and emotional management are becoming too personal and are curious as to how the employer will utilize this information. As an applicant what rights do you have regarding this information that is collected? What type of information does it classify as?

You are using an app to manage the heating, lighting and security in your house. You learn of a breach in the app database, where customers data was compromised. The company has not contacted you regarding the breach and you had to learn from the news instead. What responsibilities do you think the company should have? What steps should you take if the company does not resolve/take responsibility for the breach?

You are using a social networking app. Concerning news regarding its new CEO and novel data management regulations changes cause you to be disappointed with the app and wish to leave but retain your pictures and past uploads. How should you proceed? What would you do if the app allows you to disable your account but retains your information? Is the uploaded information yours to claim?

Your employer is asking you to fill in a form regarding your personal information for company insurance purposes. You realize the questions are too personal and think that some of them may be classified as sensitive information (i.e., health, religion, ethnicity, sexual orientation). What kind of information do you think is sensitive? Does your employer have the right to demand this type of information in the workplace setting? Why is this data different from data such as your name and age?

Tier 3 (Red)

You have been using a Fitness app to keep track of your workouts and meals. You recently heard about a new app with more advanced features and want to try it out. Instead of starting from scratch, you remembered that you have the right to take personal data with you. So, you asked the app provider's customer services to give you a copy of all your data (including workouts and meals data) stored in the app. You received an email saying that your request cannot be doable. Would you agree with the email that you received, why?

You notice that a colleague from your work often takes confidential documents home. While it is against the policy of the company you work in, upon your inquiry, your colleague just shrugs it off, telling you that "he was doing it for years now". Although you do not want to cause any problems to him and his evaluation in the company, you notice that those documents concern your customer base and allow for the re-

identification of people engaged in a clinical trial that is still ongoing. How would you deal with such a situation?

Upon examination of the clinical trial results, you fail to notice that you uploaded them to your personal cloud (assume that the cloud uploads all your files that were downloaded to your personal computer). After the clinical trials end, you notice that the cloud provider reported a series of security breaches, and your data was probably compromised as a result. Taking that into consideration, it is highly probable that all the information about the clinical trial (including patients' personal data) was also compromised as a result. Elaborate on your code of conduct.

Because your team was assigned a project that was long overdue, you worked overtime for more than a week. On a Friday afternoon, you receive a phone call from a person who allegedly works on the same project. You are asked to share confidential information (i.e., credentials) that allow them to establish an SSH connection to your company's server. Without thinking much – and tired by the ongoing crunch – you just provide them with a default login and a password. After the connections hangs up, you just realize your mistake. What would you do next?

You work in a middle-sized company as a data engineer. It is your first week in this job and you basically don't know anyone yet. As you carry instructions provided by HR to finish your setup, you notice that all your servers' set-up follow a very strange Privilege Access Management (PAM). More precisely, all the new users are operating on a super-user account basis with all the root privileges. You start to worry about this, as you know it amounts to a high-security risk. How would you proceed?

You are working in the HR office of an international firm and are analyzing location and performance data for employees. You realize you are meant to adhere to certain principles to be a lawful data controller and data processor. Considering data is collected from multiple countries (some of which are not subject to the European regulations) which regulations should you adhere to? Which principles characterize data controller and data processor responsibilities?

You are a guard at a prison where AI is used to assess the chance of recidivism in use. You realize that the algorithm consistently assesses individuals of certain ethnicities to be at greater risk of recidivism which leads to less favorable outcomes for them in terms of parole and bail. Your observation is anecdotal at this point, but you have faith the status quo is unjust and wish to take action. What would you do? Is it the algorithm, the software developers or the management who is responsible for the unequal treatment of prisoners?

There is a new global health crisis, and it is rapidly threatening an increasing number of lives. You are working in the Ministry of Health and are designing an algorithm to trace the disease in order to manage prevention. The public is hesitant to participate due to the spread of misinformation and bypassing certain privacy laws might be beneficial in the process of saving lives. Does the right to health take precedence over privacy? How would you incentivize reluctant individuals to participate in the attempt to control the disease?

You work in a cybersecurity firm. You are outsourced by a hospital to categorize and protect their EHR data. In this process the firm grants you access to all their data. Do you have the right to complete access to non-anonymized data? What factors should you consider when assessing security for health data compared to other types of data?

All the material composing the full board game kit are available and stored under an open access licence on Zenodo with DOI number: [10.5281/zenodo.17250821](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17250821).¹⁰

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